

Preparation and Characterization of Bis-Dithiocarbamato di-*p*-Tolyl Tin(IV)

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Bis-Dithiocarbamato di-*p*-tolyltin(IV), i.e., $(p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}'\text{R}')_2$ (where $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$; $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$ and $\text{R}'=-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5, -\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or $\text{RR}'=\text{morpholine, 4-methylpiperidine and N-piperazine}$), were prepared by the reaction of di-*p*-tolyltin(IV) dichloride with the sodium salt of respective dithiocarbamate acid in acetone medium in the stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 2.

The compounds have been duly characterized on the basis of infrared and nmr spectroscopic data. Anisobidentate nature of dithiocarbamate moiety has been suggested in these compounds.

In recent years a great deal of work has been reported on the synthesis and structural chemistry of organotin(IV) dithiocarbamates. The interesting aspect of organotin(IV) dithiocarbamates lies in the fact that unlike other metals or organometal dithiocarbamates, dithiocarbamate moiety in tin(IV) dithiocarbamates can be bonded to central tin atom either through one sulphur or both of the sulphur atoms of dithiocarbamate ligand.

Spectroscopic investigations including ir and uv spectral studies on various types of organotin(IV) dithiocarbamates suggest that in triorganotin(IV) dithiocarbamates $\text{R}_3\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}'\text{R}')$ or $\text{RSnCl}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}'\text{R}')_2$, the ligand behaves as monodentate^{1,8} whereas in diorganotin(IV) *bis* dithiocarbamates, the dtc ligand acts as bidentate moiety⁴⁻⁹. However, the crystallographic studies on $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Sn}(\text{IV})-\text{[S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_2$ show that dtc ligand is bonded to tin metal atom in an unsymmetrical fashion with two different Sn-S bond lengths i.e., 2.48 and 2.78 Å. This situation of one 'normal' and one 'weak' Sn-S bond lengths is consistent with the result obtained using Mossbauer spectroscopy¹¹ and has led to the coining of the term "anisobidentate" nature of these ligands in these tin(IV) compounds.

The present work deals with the synthesis of new *bis* disubstituted dithiocarbamato-di-*p*-tolyltin(IV) of the type, $(p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}'\text{R}')_2$ (where $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$; $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7, \text{R}'=-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5, -\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or $\text{RR}'=\text{morpholine, 4-methylpiperidine, N-methylpiperazine}$) and characterisation of these with the help of ir and nmr spectral studies.

Experimental

Sodium salts of N,N-disubstituted dithiocarbamic acid of the type $\text{NaS}_2\text{CNR}'\text{R}'$ (where

$\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$; $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7, \text{R}'=\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $\text{RR}'=\text{morpholine, 4-methylpiperidine, N-methyl piperazine}$) were prepared in good yield in aqueous solution by the reaction of an appropriate secondary amine, carbon disulphide and sodium hydroxide as described by Klopping *et al*¹². Since the salts contain water of crystallization they were dried first in vacuum over P_2O_5 at room temperature and then at 110° until their spectra showed no trace of water.

Tetra-*p*-tolyltin(IV) was prepared by Wurtz reaction, using a mixture of *p*-chlorotoluene (50.6 gm; 0.4 mol), sodium metal (18.4 gm; 0.8 mol) and tin tetrachloride (26.6 gm; 0.1 mol) in hydrocarbon solvents¹³.

Di-*p*-tolyltin(IV) dichloride was prepared by disproportionation reaction of tetra-*p*-tolyltin(IV) and tin tetrachloride.

Bis-N,N-dimethyldithiocarbamato-di-*p*-tolyltin(IV): To a solution of di-*p*-tolyltin dichloride (0.371 gm; 0.001 mol) in dry acetone (60 ml) was added with constant stirring, a solution of sodium salt of N,N-dimethyldithiocarbamate (0.286 gm; 0.002 mol). The mixture was refluxed for half an hour and then kept at room temperature for half an hour and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated under vacuum to give a yellow solid. The yellow solid upon recrystallization from dichloromethane and petroleum ether gave a light yellow solid corresponding to the formula $(p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2)_2$ with 80% yield, m. p. 137°.

Similarly, *bis*-dialkyldithiocarbamate-*p*-tolyltin(IV), viz., N,N-di-isopropyl, N,N-methyl phenyl, N,N-methyl benzyl, N,N-ethyl benzyl, N-methylpiperazine, 4-methylpiperidine and morpholine dithiocarbamate di-*p*-tolyltin(IV) complexes were prepared.

Analytical data of the complexes are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF DI-*p*-TOLYL TIN(IV)

Compounds	m.p. °C	Analysis Calculated (Found)%			
		C	H	N	Sn
1. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂] ₂	187	44.38 (44.70)	4.80 (5.00)	5.18 (5.20)	21.95 (20.75)
2. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(C ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂	140	48.96 (48.40)	5.70 (5.92)	4.92 (4.50)	19.90 (20.00)
3. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(C ₆ H ₇) ₂] ₂	205	51.47 (51.22)	6.48 (6.96)	4.28 (3.98)	18.08 (18.86)
4. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(CH ₃)(C ₆ H ₄ OH) ₂] ₂	143	55.43 (55.80)	4.90 (4.80)	4.04 (4.12)	17.18 (17.40)
5. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(C ₆ H ₅)(C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃)] ₂	169	56.61 (56.91)	5.24 (5.29)	3.88 (3.80)	17.37 (18.00)
6. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(C ₆ H ₇)(C ₆ H ₄ OH) ₂] ₂	156	57.70 (57.20)	5.60 (5.70)	3.78 (3.42)	15.76 (15.40)
7. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(CH ₃)(C ₆ H ₅)] ₂	170	54.15 (52.78)	4.51 (5.10)	4.21 (4.10)	17.86 (18.02)
8. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(C ₆ H ₄ O) ₂] ₂	249	46.10 (45.40)	4.80 (5.20)	4.48 (4.34)	18.00 (18.80)
9. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂ NOH] ₂	172	47.94 (47.20)	5.58 (4.78)	8.60 (8.42)	18.12 (18.00)
10. L.Sn[S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂ CH-CH ₃] ₂	165	51.79 (51.46)	5.85 (5.10)	4.31 (4.00)	18.19 (17.94)

L=(*p*-OH, C₆H₄)₂

Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 grating spectrometer in KBr pellets in the 4000-200 cm⁻¹ region. Proton magnetic resonance spectra were recorded at ambient temperature (28°) at a sweep width of 900 Hz with a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer. Spectra were recorded in triplicate and the average values considered. The magnetic field sweep was calibrated with standard sample of chloroform and tetramethyl silane (1%) in deuterated chloroform.

Results and Discussion

Diorganotin dithiocarbamates of the type R₂Sn(S₂CNRR')₂ (where R=R'=CH₃, C₆H₅, *i*-C₆H₇; R=CH₃, C₆H₅, *i*-C₆H₇ and R'=C₆H₅, CH₃C₆H₅; RR'=morpholine, 4-methyl piperidine, N-methyl piperazine) have been prepared in high yields by the reaction of diorganotin dichloride with anhydrous sodium salt of the respective dithiocarbamic acids, (NaS₂CNRR'), in acetone at room temperature according to the following equation

All these compounds are yellow solids with sharp melting points and are highly soluble in common organic solvents like benzene, chloroform, acetone and alcohol. These compounds are quite stable in dry and inert atmosphere at room temperature. Their conductivity measurements in nitrobenzene show them to be nonelectrolytic in nature.

IR spectra: The interpretation of the IR spectra of metal, and organometal dithiocarbamate complexes has aroused considerable interest both

diagnostically to determine the mode of coordination and as one of the means of assessing the nature of bonding in these complexes^{6,14-17}. Three main stretching modes of dithiocarbamate moiety, viz., (i) ν(C-N) in the region 1450-1550 cm⁻¹, (ii) ν(C-S) in the region 950-1050 cm⁻¹ and (iii) ν(M-S) in the region 350-400 cm⁻¹, have been taken into consideration to determine the denticity of the ligand.

The ν(C-N) band 1500 cm⁻¹ previously considered as a thiouride band¹⁸ is now accepted as arising from the vibration of a polar structure^{15,19} such as shown below:

The position of this band mainly depends on the arrangement of sulphur atoms around the central metal atom¹⁹, size of the R group on nitrogen¹⁹ and the electronic property of the NR₂ groups²⁰. A splitting in this region indicates the presence of a unidentate dithiocarbamate ligand or the presence of both monodentate and bidentate ligand²¹. However, the presence of a strong band in this region is an indication of the bidentate or anisobidentate character of the ligand. Similarly, the presence of a single band in the second region of interest i.e. 950-1000 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C-S), is an indication of bidentate character whereas the presence of two bands with a separation value >20 cm⁻¹ indicates one complexed (C-S) and one uncomplexed (C=S) group. This criterion, originally suggested by Ugo and Bonati⁶, although applied to a number of metal and organometal

dithiocarbamates of transition as well as non transition elements²²⁻²⁴, has further been modified²⁵ to accommodate the cases having unsymmetric bonding of the ligand, e.g., $Ti(Et_2dtc)_4$ or of ligands of different denticity in the same complex, e.g., $Sn(R_2dtc)_4$. The modification suggested was that the dtc ligand would be monodentate only if the separation value of the two bands, present in 1000 cm^{-1} region, is more than 20 cm^{-1} and a separation value less than 20 cm^{-1} is an indication either of an unsymmetric ligand or ligands with mixed denticity.

A number of dialkyltin(IV) bis-dithiocarbamates were shown to have dtc moieties acting as bidentate ligand because of the presence of single absorption bands due to $\nu(C-N) \sim 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu(C-S) \sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ⁶⁻⁷. However, later studies by Vries and Herber¹¹ on such complexes revealed that dtc groups were not bidentate but anisobidentate (from the greek word meaning unequal and referring to the interaction between a metal and a bidentate ligand having two identical atoms involved in unequal bonding structure). Their characterisation were based upon the presence of single band due to $\nu(C-S) \sim 980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a ligand mode $\sim 900\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In present case, the analyses of the ir spectra of some new di-*p*-tolyltin(IV) bis dithiocarbamates indicate an anisobidentate character of the dtc ligands in these complexes because of the following reasons :

(i) There is present only one absorption band due to $\nu(C=S) \sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This broadening of band $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be explained as although both the sulphur atoms of dtc group participate in bonding to the tin metal atom, there is a slight difference in the $\nu(Sn-S)$ bands. The difference may however be too small to be resolved into two peaks.

(ii) Ligand vibration mode $\sim 900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is also present in all these complexes as observed by Vries and Herber¹¹.

(iii) In the far ir, two absorption peaks are observed in the region $350-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating thereby two M-S stretches.

Further, the presence of one bidentate ligand in these complexes is excluded as there is no splitting in the $\nu(C-N)$ and $\nu(C-S)$ regions. It is further supported by 1H nmr studies.

The presence of two bands $\sim 580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these complexes may be assigned as the $Sn-C(asy)$ and $Sn-C(sym)$ stretching modes respectively and suggest that the $(C-Sn-C)$ moiety is not linear. Thus the molecule deviates from the *trans* geometry.

The 1H nmr spectra of N, N-dithiocarbamate complexes of di-*p*-tolyltin(IV) were recorded in $CDCl_3$ and the data showed that N-bonded R groups are equivalent in these complexes due to the following reasons.

TABLE 2—MOLAR CONDUCTANCE OF $(p-CH_3C_6H_4)_2SnS_2CNRR)_2$

Compounds	Conductance $ohm^{-1}cm^{-2}mole^{-1}$	Molarity
1. $L Sn[S_2ON(OH)_2]_2$	1.2	0.5
2. $L Sn[S_2ON(C_2H_5)_2]_2$	1.4	0.5
3. $L Sn[S_2ON(C_6H_5)_2]_2$	1.0	0.5
4. $L Sn[S_2CN(CH_3)(C_6H_5CH_2)]_2$	0.97	0.5
5. $L Sn[S_2CN(C_2H_5)(C_6H_5CH_2)]_2$	0.95	0.5
6. $L Sn[S_2CN(O_2H_5)(C_6H_5CH_2)]_2$	0.93	0.5
7. $L Sn[S_2CN(CH_3)(C_6H_5)]_2$	0.96	0.5
8. $L Sn[S_2ONOC_2H_5O]_2$	0.84	0.5
9. $L Sn[S_2CN(CH_3)_2NOH_2]_2$	0.86	0.5
10. $L Sn[S_2ON(CH_3)_2CHCH_3]_2$	0.90	0.5

$L = (p-CH_3C_6H_4)_2$

There appears only a singlet in the region 6.22–6.92 τ due to the $N-CH_3$ protons in complexes (1), (4) and (7), while in the analogous ethyl dithiocarbamate compound (2) and (5), only one type of quartet at 6.54 τ due to $N-CH_2$ and a triplet at 8.72 and 9.20 τ due to the $-CH_3$ protons of the ethyl group are observed. In case of methyl benzyl, ethyl benzyl, isopropyl benzyl and methyl phenyl compounds (4-7) the presence of a singlet in the region 2.18 to 3.0 τ is correlated with phenyl protons, whereas the proton signals due to $-CH_2$ protons of the benzyl group compound (4-6), appear in the region 5.06 to 5.28 τ ^{11,26}. The N-isopropyl group in compound (3) and (6) is well characterized by a multiplet at 5.5 τ and of a heptlet at 5.2 τ due to $N-CH_2$ protons and a doublet at 8.62 and 8.72 τ due to $-CH_3$ protons of the isopropyl group, respectively.

The proton signals of the morphyl group in compound (8) appear at 5.9 τ ($O-CH_2$) and 6.2 τ ($N-CH_2$) and confirm the equivalence of both the morphyl groups in this complex⁴. The N-methyl piperazine group in compound (9) is inferred from the presence of two types of proton signals i.e., one triplet at 5.5 τ due to the $-CH_2$ on nitrogen attached with CS_2 group and another at 7.3 τ due to CH_2 protons on another nitrogen atom of the piperazyl group. Furthermore, a singlet at 7.5 τ (due to the $-CH_3$ protons), a doublet at 4.5 τ (due to $N-CH_2$ protons), another doublet at 9.0 τ (due to $C-CH_2$ protons) together with a multiplet at 3.3 τ (due to $-C-H$ protons) characterize the 4-methyl piperazyl group in compound (10).

The tin bonded $P-CH_2C_6H_4-$ groups in compounds (1-10) are characterized by the presence of three types of resonance signals i.e. a singlet in the region 7.5–7.92 τ due to CH_2 protons and a doublet due to $(CH)_2$ (*meta*) protons in the region 2.1-2.90 τ and another in the region 1.7-2.3 τ due to $(CH)_2$ (*ortho*) protons of the phenyl ring^{27,28}.

Furthermore, the above observed positions of proton signals of the dithiocarbamate group suggest

an anisobidentate group in these complexes as *bis-p*-tolyl *bis* dimethyl dithiocarbamatotin(IV) compound (I) shows. The resonance signals due to N-CH₃ protons in this complex appears at 6.6 τ. This value is intermediate between monodentate and pure bidentate^{2,9} dithiocarbamate complexes and corresponds very well to the analogous *bis* alkyl *bis* dithiocarbamatotin(IV) complexes⁴. It should be noted, however, that these data refer to solution species.

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